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DIATOMIC: Impact of the Data (Use and Access) Act 2025, on Local Authorities Across the United Kingdom

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Abstract

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This report examines the impact of the Data (Use and Access) Act 2025 on Local Authorities across the United Kingdom, drawing on semi-structured interviews with five Local Authority staff members. Findings indicate that the Act has had a positive but measured impact so far, with changes felt more culturally than legislatively. While benefits include improved data sharing and reduced barriers to health data, key challenges remain around staff misinterpretation of the Act and the responsible use of AI. Adequate training and human oversight will be critical to the Act's successful long-term implementation.

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Introduction

1.1 Aim of the Research

The introduction of the Data (Use and Access) Act 2025 has, and will, lead to changes within the ways that Local Authorities across Great Britain handle and share data. However, it is yet to be seen how comprehensive an understanding of any impacts or challenges from the Data (Use and Access) Act 2025 are within the public domain.

In this research, we focus on participants' knowledge of the GDPR Act 2018 and Data (Use and Access) Act 2025, the positive changes and challenges that the introduction of the DUA Act 2025 has brought, and any potential future impacts from the act.

1.2 Historic Data Protection in the UK

The UK's Data Protection legislation originates in the Data Protection act of 1984, as a result of the growing importance of data in the economy and the proliferation of computing resources amongst business, government and the public. Further to this, the Computer Misuse Act 1990 and the Data Protection Act 1998 (which aligned with similar EU legislation on data protection) further expanded on principles originally laid down in the 1984 legislation. Broadly, the acts were the first to legislate for principles related to the collection and sharing of information related to a specific person, their personal details, demographics, contact details, employment history, and a range of other characteristics. Across both the 1984 and 1998 acts, special characteristics which might enable someone to be discriminated against were also recognised, such as race and sexuality. Crucially, the 1984 act had only applied to information which is processed automatically, whereas the 1998 act also included paper records. The 1998 act therefore was extended to any information collected in any manner according to a set of categories. The 1998 act established that data should only be processed lawfully, it should be accurate and kept up to date where necessary and that it should be relevant. Furthermore, it stated that data should not be kept for excessive amounts of time, although in practice the legislation did not specify what amount of time that was.

1.3 GDPR and the Updated DPA 2018

Although the UK was in the process of leaving the EU by the time GDPR enforcement began in earnest, the equivalent principles are coded into the Data Protection Act 2018, which superseded the 1998 act. GDPR was widely recognised as one of the most comprehensive privacy acts in the world when it was implemented and made a set of substantial changes. It retained characteristics on lawful use, consent and types of processing that had been in place in prior EU Data Directives (1995 in particular), but primarily it established formal definitions for the types of data considered personal information, the types of data that were under special characteristics, the roles and responsibilities that organisations needed to establish (such as data processor and data controller). However, another major aspect of the act related to the rights of the individual to understand what information was being held on them, for what purposes, and to request that it be deleted in certain cases. The formalisation of subject access requests was a major change that aimed to rebalance the information asymmetry between data processors and data subjects.

1.4 Data (Use and Access) Act 2025

The Data (Use and Access) Act makes amendments to the previous acts to address a set of emerging challenges that have arisen in the implementation of GDPR, and a set of successes in the UK economy. For challenges, it was recognised that GDPR had prevented the development of mechanisms to share data between organisations, even when consent had been given by the data subject themselves. This resulted in data being shared via less secure methods, such as downloading spreadsheets and emailing them, which introduced avenues for data breaches. Furthermore, two initiatives pioneered the sharing of information for public benefit. The first was Open Banking, which enabled much faster current account switching, easier access to finance, a range of new competitor banks, and smoother payment processing. The second was the National Underground Asset Register, which collected (and now compels the sharing of) a vast amount of information from local authorities,

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Introduction continued

gas, water, telecoms and anyone else with buried assets.

Principally, the 2025 act explicitly implements a set of new lawful processing reasons, explicitly codes the sharing proposed in Open Banking (consumer focused and with consent) into law, whilst relaxing some of the restrictions on sharing information between agencies or companies that carry out public functions.

For example, Section 71 states “This measure clarifies the circumstances in which “further processing” or data re-use is compatible with the original purpose, including when personal data is being re-used for a very different purpose from which it was originally collected. For example, when a company may wish to disclose personal data for crime prevention.”

Methodology

2.1 Selection of Qualitative Analysis Method

To conduct this qualitative analysis, there were multiple different formats to consider. Options included conducting surveys, hosting a roundtable discussion, document analysis, in-person interviews, and online interviews.

Surveys were discounted due to the range of interactivity that would be received, with the potential for participants to respond with short answers when not pushed for more detailed responses. Despite the potential for a large base answers, these answers may not include the detail that could be obtained through the use of other methods.

Round table discussions were considered, however, were discounted due to the need to have each participant in the same in-person space, and also for the opportunity for each participant to be able to deliver their opinion in an individual format, separate from other Local Authorities.

Document analysis, which includes the reading and comprehension of the original Data (Use and Access) Act 2025, was not chosen as the lead method due to the appreciation that interaction with the impacted parties would be more suitable, rather than a process of aiming to understanding the potential impacts. Despite not being the main chosen method for the qualitative analysis, comprehension of the DUA Act 2025 was undertaken, to provide a basis of understanding to the interviewer to be able to most suitably conduct the qualitative data collection.

The method of data collection that was found to be the most suitable, was the format of an online interview. Online, one-on-one, interviews were chosen to enable an easier organisation of interviews, rather than in-person. A one-on-one interview format was chosen to allow for conversation to take place between the interviewer and participant, and for the participant to feel comfortable within the interview. The interview consisted of a semi-structured format, focused around six main questions, with follow-up questions asked where necessary. The interview was carried out with the participant covering any information that they wanted to provide, but all personal, geographic or any other identifiable information has been removed, ensuring that the participants and their Local Authorities remain anonymous throughout.

2.2 Formation of Interview Questions

To create the questions that were asked in the interview, the final research purposes were considered. It was proposed to identify the story that the interview would follow, and how the questions would begin to build an understanding of the participant, and work through their knowledge of the Data (Use and Access) Act, understanding and appreciating any impacts or challenges that the Act has either already brought to the Local Authority, or will in the future.

Therefore, the initial questions, which were used to build a picture of the participant, were focused on the participants role within their Local Authority, and their understanding of the GDPR Act 2018, and its relevance to their role.

The interview continued with questions focused on the participants understanding of the new Data (Use and Access) Act 2025 and any new laws that have or will come into place as a result of the Act, and an overview of the impact that the Act has had so far.

This was followed by questions more specifically relating to the positive changes that the Data (Use and Access) Act 2025 has lead to, and also any challenges that have arisen as a result of the Act.

The final structured question was related to the future impact of the Data (Use and Access) Act 2025, and any positive changes or challenges that may arise within the next few years, as a result of the Data (Use and Access) Act 2025.

Further to these questions, unstructured questions were also asked where it was felt necessary to allow the participant to provide more detail on specific areas.

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Examples of the structured questions are, and are not limited to;

- What is your current understanding of the Data (Use and Access) Act 2025?
- What is your understanding of the impact of the new Data (Use and Access) Act 2025 for your Local Authority?
- How has the data sharing/availability within your Local Authority been positively impacted by the the new Data (Use and Access) Act 2025?
- How do you see the Data (Use and Access) Act 2025 impacting your Local Authority in the future?

2.3 Selection of Interview Participants

Interview invites were sent out to Local Authority staff members from multiple different Local Authorities, across a variety of roles that were relevant to the Data Act, with the intention to interview to an array of people through the interview process, gaining an understanding of the impact of the Data Act from multiple angles.

There were five responses in total, each agreeing to take part in the interview process. These interviews took part over the course of three weeks, in the form of an online interview.

2.4 Interview Process

The online interviews were carried out using Microsoft Teams, and each of the participants gave permission for the interviews to be transcribed, with additional audio recording, by the AI transcription service provided by Microsoft Teams.

At the end of each interview, the AI transcription service provided a complete transcript of the interview, alongside the audio recording from the interview. At this stage, qualitative analysis was able to be performed on each of the interviews. Each of the transcripts had any identifying information removed from the transcripts, including names, locations and job titles, to ensure that any comparisons that were drawn were made with a complete non-bias.

These interviews were then thoroughly read, highlighting key points and quotes from each of the five participants, to build a picture of the knowledge of the DUAA of each of the interviewees, and the impact of the DUAA for their respective Local Authorities. Using this understanding, comparisons can be drawn from the five interviews, both drawing on similar answers from the participants, but also having an awareness of the differences between the answers.

This section explores the findings from each interview, broken into the questions that were asked to the participants, their respective responses, and the comparisons and similarities that can be drawn from these answers, between different members of Local Authority staff.

3.1 Interview Comparisons

3.1.1 Awareness of the Data (Use and Access) Act 2025

Each of the five participants were aware of the Data (Use and Access) Act 2025. Two of the participants, who have policy-facing roles, had a greater awareness and stronger understanding of the DUAA, with an appreciation of specific outputs from the DUAA. The three participants that have more operational roles were each aware of the principles of the DUAA and the impact of the DUAA for both their roles and their authority, but did not have explicit awareness of specific outputs from the DUAA. In each of these cases for the three operational participants, they had strong connections within their Local Authority that could inform them on any relevant laws or amendments from the DUAA.

3.1.2 Impact of the GDPR Act 2018

Building a picture of the participants' knowledge around this area, information was gathered on the participants' understanding of the GDPR Act 2018, and the impact that this had on their role and Local Authority. The GDPR Act 2018 was described by each of the participants as providing a governing framework and accountability principles within their Local Authorities. Across the interviews, GDPR was described as providing "new obligations, new provisions", while also providing a framework to cover "from an organisational risk perspective". The GDPR Act 2018 also "tightened up the requirements" in terms of documenting all evidence. From each of the interviews, the overwhelming message that was conveyed was that the GDPR Act 2018 had a large impact on their roles and also the running of their Local Authorities, bringing in impactful changes for the better.

3.1.3 Impact of the Data (Use and Access) Act 2025

Relating to the Data (Use and Access) Act 2025, each of the participants believed that DUAA is having, and will have, less of an impact than the GDPR Act. Two participants cited that the DUAA is having a more cultural impact rather than legislative, whilst another participant stated that the DUAA has "really codified what was previously ICO guidance", and "now it's not just guidance, it's statutory law."

One participant commented that the phased implementation of the DUAA, and the preparation for the Data Protection and Digital Information Bill that will not become law (due to changes in the Government), has led to frustration in addressing the changes. This participant also indicated that there was preparation taking place for the new requirements for organisations to have a complaints procedure in place, which comes into effect on June 19 2026.

3.1.4 Positive Impact of the Data (Use and Access) Act 2025

Throughout the interviews, from each of the participants, there were mentions of numerous of positive impacts that the DUAA has been having on Local Authorities, based on the ability to use and share data differently. In one interview, there was focus on how the DUAA was strengthening research, by being able to "reuse any data that's held". A second interviewee said that the DUAA was "making data more accessible and for people understanding the pathways, the legal gateways for sharing data", whilst "with health data, which has been a real barrier for many, many years, we should start to see some of those barriers disappear".

A third participant stated that they think "it'll help us be more effective in dealing with citizens and council business, it gives us the ability to use data for a decent purpose, but also protect the rights of the data subjects".

It was also said by an interviewee, that the DUAA "codified a lot of what are recognised compatible purposes for re-sharing information or even reusing information within the council", supporting the statements that the DUAA has enabled a more natural data sharing process.

Supporting how the DUAA has had a positive, but not revolutionary, impact, a participant stated that “it felt as if it was supporting the journey we were on, rather than thinking, stop, we’ve got to revisit everything we’re doing here”.

Across the interviews, two separate participants commented on the use of dashboards to be able to summarise data from periods of time and different departments, highlighting a significant positive that enables greater sharing across the Local Authorities. It was stated that one participant has “been able to give them that in a dashboard where they can spend half an hour in a morning looking at exactly what’s happened in the last 24 hours”, and that “we have an initiative around looking at a data platform with various sort of dashboards that make data more available and this is in areas like public health, housing, adult social care”.

3.1.5 Challenges/Risks from the Data (Use and Access) Act 2025

Despite the positives from the Data (Use and Access) Act 2025, there are also challenges and risks that have developed. One comment that was observed several times throughout the interview process, was around the potential increased number of subject access requests. One participant suggested that an increased number of subject access requests would lead to a requirement for more staff members within the Local Authority, whilst another interviewee indicated that an increased number of subject access requests would result in members of staff within the Local Authority to be moved into different areas to aid with the increased demand. A separate interviewee suggested that with the increased AI use, the number of subject access requests and complaints will likely rise, as people will raise complaints through ease of access.

Relating to the use of AI for data within Local Authorities, several participants discussed the use of AI as a risk. One participant stated that “AI is really good at merging data together and producing results”, however, that it has merged data that should not have been merged together. On the use of AI, an interviewee suggested that a concern is the overuse of AI where human intervention is necessary, saying “it’s co-pilot, not autopilot”.

The largest concern, that came from four of the five participants, is based on misinterpretation and misunderstanding of the Data (Use and Access) Act 2025. This feedback was received in terms of the training that was and will be completed by staff members, not necessarily determining that the staff members are then able to apply the knowledge from the training. There was a large consensus that the lack of understanding of the Act may result in a large barrier, which was shared by three participants. Participants suggested that the Act may be interpreted as giving broader meaning than it actually does and that different staff members may interpret the Act in different forms.

3.1.6 Future Impact of the Data (Use and Access) Act 2025

When questioned on the future impact of the Data (Use and Access) Act 2025, participants commonly built on the positives and challenges that had been mentioned throughout their interview.

Citing positive impacts for the future, the DUAA was suggested to be enabling for the future, rather than imposing restrictions on current practises. It was discussed throughout the interviews that the impact of the Act had not been fully witnessed so far, but that the core principles of the DUAA were positive and building on the GDPR Act and Data Protection Act 2018. Four of the five participants talk of the possibility and potential for working with both neighbouring authorities, and with data sharing and data governing bodies, such as the DVLA. Working with these organisations was cited as positive for both data sharing agreements, but also to best interpret the new legislation.

Conversely, the interpretation of the DUAA 2025 into the future was seen as a longterm challenge by four of the interviewees. Tying to this, three participants were conscious that there may need to be structural changes needed within Local Authorities due to the potential increased demand from the DUAA.

Regarding the use of AI, there were several different opinions provided throughout the interviews. One participant was optimistic that AI involvement would have a positive future impact for Local Authorities, whilst two other participants were wary of its use, mentioning the need for human oversight.

Throughout the interviews with each of the participants, a much clearer understanding of the impact of the Data (Use and Access) Act 2025 on different Local Authorities was attained. A discussion of the participants responses allows for an appreciation of the answers given, and to build a bigger picture for wider understanding of the Act.

Positively, each of the five participants that agreed to take part in the interview process each had a depth of understanding relating to the GDPR Act 2018 and the Data (Use and Access) Act 2025. This knowledge, combined with their full understanding of their roles within their Local Authority, enabled thoroughly investigative conversation into the impacts of the DUAA.

During the interviews, it was discussed how much of an impact the GDPR Act 2018 had had on legislation and in providing a governing framework for data use and sharing procedures, whilst tightening up requirements of Local Authorities. Comparatively, the Data (Use and Access) Act, which was designed to make amendments to the previous acts, including looking to address challenges that have arisen due to GDPR, was frequently described in the interview process as having less of a tangible impact, with the impact that is being witnessed seen as more cultural rather than focused on transforming legislation.

This is a positive step towards a more coherent and widely understood data use and sharing legislature. After the implementation of GDPR 2018, there were significant changes to procedures throughout Local Authorities, and it is beneficial to understand that the implementation of the DUAA 2025 has not led to such widespread changes, at least not yet. Any changes that have been (or will be) witnessed within Local Authorities are built on making positive amendments to the GDPR and DPA Acts from 2018. These changes being observed as more cultural than transformative is positive to hear from the participants, as this echoes that the amendments are making beneficial changes, rather than rewriting legislation.

Of the positives discussed by participants, one key point that was shared by multiple interviewees was around the use (and reuse) and sharing ability of data. The ability to reuse data held by the Local Authority was discussed as a large strength for enabling higher quality research and a much smoother data sharing process within councils. The use of dashboards for different organisations to be able to view multiple data sources at one time was frequently mentioned as a large benefit to the DUAA, enabling a much clearer communication of data.

It was discussed that the DUAA is starting to take barriers down in terms of sharing health data, which is a strong benefit for a much healthier data system. The DUAA has allowed the participants to be more effective in communicating with local residents and businesses, with the act supporting and enabling the journey that the Local Authorities are on in terms of data sharing.

However, despite the Data (Use and Access) Act 2025 being seen as having large positives, there are also barriers to its successful implementation and challenges that are arising from the act.

These barriers to its implementation largely lie in the correct interpretation of the act. To ensure a successful implementation of the act, each of the organisations that the DUAA is impacting should each comprehensively understand the amendments and new legislation that is being implemented. However, from the interviews with these participants, it is evident that this is a challenge.

Throughout interviews, it was suggested that training measures that are undertaken to help staff members interpret the DUAA may not necessarily lead to successful interpretation. This misinterpretation may result in a barrier to an efficient and prompt implementation of the DUAA, hindering Local Authorities for the coming months.

Other challenges were discussed, including the risk that the number of subject access requests that are received by Local Authorities may rise significantly. A rise in subject access requests, compared to pre-DUAA, would lead to higher demand on Local Authorities. This, according to the interviewees, could lead to the need for new staff to be hired by Local Authorities or for staff to be moved into different roles within each respective Local Authorities.

The use of Artificial Intelligence was considered as a positive and a risk by

different participants, and it evidently a topic that should be considered in relation to the DUAA into the future. The positives of AI were suggested to be that the Data (Use and Access) Act 2025 has enabled AI-supported decision making, whilst two different participants suggested that it should be ensured that there should be human oversight used in these processes, as there is a chance that using AI for data merging could lead to data issues.

It is clear that AI is the future for Local Authorities, and it is positive to hear that one participant is optimistic for its benefit for their Local Authority. Furthermore, it is positive to hear that two participants are wary of the challenges of using AI, but are not fully against its use, suggesting that the use of AI is not negative, but does come with reasonable challenges for its use.

At the completion of these interviews, suggestions can be made that would likely benefit the successful implementation of the Data (Use and Access) Act 2025. Firstly, one major point is to ensure that all relevant staff members that are affected by the Data (Use and Access) Act 2025 are suitably trained on the correct implementation of the Act. This would also include training around the use of AI that has been enabled by the Act, and its role in data sharing across Local Authorities.

With these steps taken and considering each of the positives mentioned by the participants, the impact of the Data (Use and Access) Act 2025 is beneficial for both data use and data sharing within Local Authorities and external organisations in the United Kingdom.

As the Data (Use and Access) Act only received Royal Assent in June 2025, there has not been a considerable amount of time for the act to have taken hold. It would be useful to complete further research into the impact of the DUAA after a further year of its implementation has taken place, to gather a deeper understanding of its impact.

Conclusion

To summarise the five interviews with different staff members from Local Authorities across the United Kingdom, the Data (Use and Access) Act 2025 has had a notable positive impact already. The impact of this most recent data related act has not been as significant as previous acts (GDPR 2018), as the DUAA has built on this act and amended it to address challenges from the integration of previous acts.

The Data (Use and Access) Act 2025 has begun to break down barriers in data sharing and data availability, however, it must be ensured that there is adequate training undertaken by relevant staff, to ensure that the DUAA is accurately interpreted across Local Authorities.

The use of Artificial Intelligence within the data sector is growing, and the DUAA is enabling AI-supported decision making, but any tasks using AI to handle decisions, data or otherwise, must have a level of human oversight.

The Data (Use and Access) Act has so far had more of a cultural impact than legislative impact, and this is a positive connotation attached to building on the GDPR Act 2018. The DUAA has been in place since June 2025, and its staged implementation spans until June 2026. It is positive to see the beneficial impacts the act has had in the nine months since it received Royal Assent, however, it is important to consider the future impact that the DUAA will have on Local Authorities. This may be just in the form of the aforementioned increase demand, however, there may be further positive impacts, challenges, or risks that arise in the future.

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